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Aldehydes as Corrosion Inhibitors for 70/30 Brass in Potassium Persulphate Solutions

M. N. DESAI, D. K. SHAH & V. K. SHAH

Chemistry Department, University School of Sciences
Gujarat University, Ahmedabad-380009

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POTASSIUM persulphate solutions can be used to remove oxide layers from metal surface, hence inhibitors are necessary.

From earlier work in this laboratory it was found the furfuraldehyde^{1,2}, salicylaldehyde^{1,2} and paraldehyde² are satisfactory inhibitors for the corrosion of copper(1) and 63/37 brass² in potassium persulfate solutions. The present article reports furfuraldehyde, salicylaldehyde and paraldehyde as corrosion inhibitors for 70/30 brass in 0.2M potassium persulfate solutions.

70/30 brass supplied by M/s. Kamani Metals was used for the study. The preparation of specimens and corrosion tests were carried out as per our earlier publication³.

The effect of time on performance of inhibitors is given in Table 1. The ratios of copper and zinc going in solution are given in Table 2. The influence of current density on the cathode and anode potentials of 70/30 brass in 0.2M K₂S₂O₈ in the presence and absence of inhibitors is given in fig. 1. (Table 1, Fig. 1)

Influence of current density on the cathode and anode potentials of 70/30 brass in 0.2M potassium persulphate in the presence and absence of inhibitors

- 0.2M K₂S₂O₈
- ×—× 26.1 ml/l paraldehyde
- 8.7 ml/l Salicylaldehyde
- △—△ 2.17 ml/l Salicylaldehyde
- 34.8 ml/l Furfuraldehyde

TABLE 1

Inhibitor concentration ml/l.	70/30 Brass — Potassium Persulphate				
	Corrosion loss of Specimen (mg./dm ²) and % inhibition for an immersion period of : (Values in the bracket represent percentage inhibition)				
	5 min.	15 min.	30 min.	60 min.	90 min.
Paraldehyde					
0.00 ml/l	202.5	564.3	1152.0	2176.0	3042.0
17.40 ml/l	(—)	(—)	(—)	(—)	(—)
26.10 ml/l	3.6	9.7	7.5	33.8	53.2
	(98.2)	(98.3)	(99.4)	(98.4)	(98.3)
Furfuraldehyde					
26.10 ml/l	—	—	6.1	15.2	30.3
	(—)	(—)	(99.5)	(99.3)	(99.0)
Salicylaldehyde					
4.35 ml/l	1.1	1.9	21.3	113.1	504.2
	(99.4)	(99.6)	(98.2)	(94.8)	(81.5)
8.70 ml/l	0.3	0.3	1.4	6.1	8.3
	(99.8)	(99.8)	(99.9)	(99.8)	(99.7)
	5.3	9.1	16.1	40.1	60.4
	(97.3)	(98.4)	(98.6)	(98.1)	(97.1)

Observations : The rate of corrosion of 70/30 brass in 0.2M potassium persulphate increases with time.

Paraldehyde : At 17.40 ml/l concentration, paraldehyde effectively retards the corrosion of 70/30 brass in 0.2M potassium persulphate for all the duration studied. At lower inhibitor concentrations, the effect of paraldehyde is immediate, but the efficiency decreases with the passage of time.

TABLE 2

Inhibitor	Ratio of copper/zinc in 0.2M (Potassium-persulphate (Values in the bracket represent inhibitor concentration in ml/l or percentage)				
	5 min.	15 min.	30 min.	60 min.	90 min.
Nil	2.65	4.04	2.15	2.58	2.25
Paraldehyde	4.98	3.79	4.69	—	3.49
	(2.17 ml/l)	(8.70 ml/l)	(8.70 ml/l)	—	(17.40 ml/l)
Salicylaldehyde	0.7	2.3	3.1	1.54	2.57
	(8.70 ml/l)	(8.70 ml/l)	(8.70 ml/l)	(8.70 ml/l)	(8.70 ml/l)

In the presence of paraldehyde, the potential values are more negative throughout than those in its absence. The potential values in the presence of 26.10 ml/l paraldehyde are more negative than those in the presence of 8.70 ml/l paraldehyde which is in good agreement with the higher efficiency with increased concentration of the inhibitor.

In the presence of 26.10 ml/l paraldehyde, there is considerable cathode polarization, the anode is also polarized to a certain extent. Thus, paraldehyde is a mixed type of inhibitor with the predominance of cathodic action.

Furfuraldehyde: In general, the efficiency of furfuraldehyde decreases with the passage of time. At 17.40 ml/l concentration, the excellent inhibitive action of furfuraldehyde is felt immediately.

In the presence of 34.80 ml/l furfuraldehyde, the potential values are more negative than those in its absence indicating its action on local cathodes. In the presence of 17.40 ml/l furfuraldehyde, the potential values are more negative upto fifteen minutes, thereafter the values are practically identical in the presence and absence of the inhibitor.

Furfuraldehyde induces strong cathode polarization. However, the effect of the inhibitor on the local anodes is not quite perceptible from the polarization measurements.

Salicylaldehyde: Salicylaldehyde is an excellent inhibitor which affords more than 98% protection to 70/30 brass even at as low a concentration as 0.43 ml/l. The optimum concentration of salicylaldehyde is 4.35 ml/l, the further increase in the inhibitor concentration induces a slight decrease in its efficiency. The efficiency of salicylaldehyde is nearly constant from fifteen to 90 min.

In the presence of 2.17 ml/l salicylaldehyde, the potential values are throughout more negative indicating its action on local cathodes. In the presence of 8.70 ml/l salicylaldehyde, the potential values are less negative than those in the presence of 2.17 ml/l salicylaldehyde which is in good agreement with the decreased efficiency of salicylaldehyde beyond, 2.17 ml/l concentration.

Salicylaldehyde induces significant cathode polarization. The anode is also polarized in the presence of salicylaldehyde. The higher inhibition action of 2.17

ml/l salicylaldehyde is evident from the increased cathode and anode polarization in its presence, as compared with the values obtained in the presence of 8.70 ml/l salicylaldehyde.

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Nitrate and Nitrite Derivatives of Diarylthallium(III) Cation

T. N. SRIVASTAVA and K. K. BAJPAI*

Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, Lucknow.

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SOME diorganothallium (III) nitrates (organo= CH_3 , C_6F_5 , and C_6H_5) have been synthesised either by the interaction of diorganothallium (III) iodide and silver nitrate^{1,2} or by heating organothallium oxide with concentrated nitric acid in glacial acetic acid³. The infrared spectra of the compounds indicate weak nitrate co-ordination resulting in a bridging structure, but the high conductance in methanol is consistent with the presence of linear R_2Ti^+ ions. Little is known about the corresponding organothallium (III) nitrites. In continuation to our studies on diarylthallium (III) derivative⁴⁻⁷ we now report the synthesis and characterisation of some diarylthallium (III) nitrates and nitrites (aryl = phenyl, o-tolyl, m-tolyl or p-tolyl).

Experimental

Diarylthallium (III) chlorides were synthesised by the reported method⁸. Other reagents of analytical grade were obtained from British Drug Houses. Dimethyl formamide was freshly distilled under reduced pressure before use in conductometric measurements.

In a typical preparation 1 m mole of diarylthallium (III) chloride in 50 ml pyridine-water mixture was treated with a concentrated aqueous solution of excess of sodium nitrate or nitrite (5 m mole) and the mixture stirred for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The precipitated diarylthallium (III) derivative was filtered, washed with water, ethanol, finally with diethyl ether and dried. The melting points, the analytical data of the compounds and their infrared active anionic absorptions are presented in Table 1.

*Present address: Indian Institute of Sugarcane Research, Lucknow (U. P.) India.